

SOME OF SEMICONDUCTORS ZONE STRUCTURE

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Quantitative calculation of the zone structure of any substance is associated with certain difficulties. This observed difficulty is primarily due to the lack of a concrete analytical expression of the potential of the crystal lattice. Therefore, in all such calculations, physical parameters that can only be calculated experimentally are usually involved in the basic formulas. Such parameters include, for example, the width of the prohibited zone, the value of the effective mass, etc. includes.

For a crystal, the one-electron problem can be solved by two types of approximations: quasi-free and quasi-bound electron approximations. Another method is the orthogonalized plane wave method, which is a convenient combination of these. Here, the wave function during the movement of the electron in the crystal is selected as a combination of plane waves, and the wave functions of the inner electrons for the atom are subtracted from them.

Keywords: Crystal, plane wave, electron layer, conductivity zone, Brillouin zone.

Introduction

For a crystal, the one-electron problem can be solved by two types of approximations: quasi-free and quasi-bound electron approximations. Another method is the orthogonalized plane wave method, which is a convenient combination of these. Here, the wave function during the movement of the electron in the crystal is selected as a combination of plane waves, and the wave functions of the inner electrons for the atom are subtracted from them. The wave functions of the internal electrons are selected as a combination of the Bloch function in the strong-binding electron approximation. Thus, the wave function of the electron in the crystal behaves as a plane wave in the interatomic space, and as an atomic wave function at the nodes (around the atoms). In this case, the solution of the problem faces certain difficulties. For example, when this method is applied to silicon and germanium crystals, it is necessary to solve an equation with 146 unknowns to get the energy expression at an arbitrary point of the Brillouin zone. In this case, the problem is solved by the application of group theory, and although it is simplified enough for points with charge-charge symmetry, 16 unknown equations are still obtained, which can be solved only by numerical calculations.

Let's look at the band structure of a few materials that have properties more typical of semiconductors.

a) Silicon and germanium crystals. As can be seen from the structure of electron layers (2), in these substances the last, partially filled layer p is the layer, where two electrons with spins parallel to each other

are located, that is, the ground state is a triplet. The band structure of silicon and germanium was calculated by German et al. using the orthogonalized plane wave method for a series of points with high symmetry in the Brillouin zone. Energy values for other points $[E(\vec{k})]$ were obtained by interpolation.

Theoretical calculations were compared with the results obtained in practice, checked and a number of corrections were made to them. The layer of both substances p is involved in the formation of conduction and valence zones. That's why it's a whistle of the approach. When constructing p the Bloch function, it is necessary to use the wavefunctions corresponding to the case (which has a triple twist if the spin is not taken into account).

As a result of the interaction, the cracking disappears and the resulting two zones (valence and conduction zones) consist of three bands each. The lanes within both zones partially intersect (overlap).

show the dependence of the energy on the wave vector in [111] and [100] directions for silicon and germanium. This dependence is different for different directions. In the conduction zone (for both substances), one of the branches of energy is located much lower than the other two. The position of the lowest minimum (absolute minimum) of this branch determines the bottom of the conduction zone.

In silicon, the absolute minimum is in the [100] direction (within the Brillouin zone). So there are 6 such minima (since there are 6 equivalent directions).

State cross-section of isoenergetic surfaces (001) plane in the isoenergetic conduction zone of silicon and germanium (a) in the valence zone of silicon and germanium (b) isoenergetic surfaces near minima in the conduction zone for germanium is shown in figure 3. Half of each ellipsoid remains in the first Brillüen zone, as its minimum points fall on the border of the Brillüen zone. Therefore, 4 complete ellipsoids differ from 8 equivalent points, that is, there are not 8, but 4 complete ellipsoids in the conduction zone. The maximum of the valence band of silicon and germanium is located at the center point of the Brillüen zone $\vec{k} = \mathbf{0}$ for all three

$$E_{1,2}(\vec{k}) = E(0) - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_0} \left[Ak^2 \pm \sqrt{B^2 k^4 + C^2 (k_x^2 k_y^2 + k_y^2 k_z^2 + k_z^2 k_x^2)} \right] \quad (2)$$

where m_0 - the mass of the free electron, A, B, C - are dimensionless constants. Silicon for $A = 4,1 \pm 0,2$; $B = 1,6 \pm 0,2$; $C = 3,3 \pm 0,5$, germanium for:

$$A = 13,0 \pm 0,2; B = 8,9 \pm 0,1;$$

$C = 10,3 \pm 0,2$ - is _ This case isoenergetic surfaces ellipsoid not to deformation It is a folded (" wrinkled ") sphere (see: photo 3). He is that energy _

$$E_{1,2}(\vec{k}) = E(0) - \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m_0} \left[A \pm \sqrt{B^2 + C^2 \sin^2 \theta (\sin^2 \varphi \cdot \cos^2 \varphi \cdot \sin^2 \theta + \cos^2 \theta)} \right]. \quad (3)$$

From angles dependent which is hit it all angles on medium the price if we take:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi \sin^2 \theta (\sin^2 \varphi \cdot \cos^2 \varphi \cdot \sin^2 \theta + \cos^2 \theta) \sin \theta d\theta d\varphi = \\ & = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left[\int_0^{2\pi} \left(\int_0^\pi \sin^5 \theta d\theta \right) \sin^2 \varphi \cos^2 \varphi d\varphi + \int_0^\pi \sin^3 \theta \cos^2 \theta d\theta \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi \right] = \\ & = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left[\frac{4\pi}{15} + \frac{8\pi}{15} \right] = \frac{1}{5}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Then:

$$E_{1,2}(\vec{k}) = E(0) - \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m_0} \left[A \pm \sqrt{B^2 + \frac{C^2}{2}} \right] \quad (5)$$

Thus, " corrugated " surfaces we sphere to the surfaces brought we were Then of holes effective mass for so one scalar quantity we get:

branches of energy. Here, two zones coincide with each other, that is, if the spin splitting is not taken into account, there is a double splitting, and the third band splits as a result of the interaction of the electron spin and the magnetic field corresponding to its orbital motion (spin -orbital interaction), and the other two separated from the lane. As a result of the spin -orbital interaction, the value of splitting is 0.035 eV for silicon and 0.28 eV for germanium.

is more complicated than the expression (1) near its maximum point for the first two branches, and is determined by the following formula: $\vec{k} = \mathbf{0}$

k_x, k_y, k_z from _ same sex dependent if also (2), this of addition character it is so that it is effective _ mass tensor from superstition use to do opportunity does not give If $\vec{k}$ in space polar read $\vec{k}_z$ with on top of each other falling spherical coordinate from the system use if we do , then expression (2.18.2). So we can write:

$$m_p^* = \frac{m_0}{A \pm \sqrt{B^2 + \frac{C^2}{5}}} \quad (6)$$

I mean each energy branch unique scalar effective mass there are:

$$m_{1p}^* = \frac{m_0}{A - \sqrt{B^2 + \frac{C^2}{5}}};$$

$$m_{2p}^* = \frac{m_0}{A + \sqrt{B^2 + \frac{C^2}{5}}}. \quad (7)$$

From expression (7). it appears whom $m_{1p}^* > m_{2p}^*$. To him according to big effective to the crowd suitable coming in the zone which is to the holes heavy holes, small effective to the crowd suitable coming in the zone which is to the holes to work light holes it is said. For example, silicon for suitable of settings values in (7). instead of if we write:

$$m_{1p}^* = 0,52m_0,$$

$$m_{2p}^* = 0,16m_0,$$

$$m_{1p}^* / m_{2p}^* = 3,3.$$

From experience received prices:

$$\frac{m_{1p}^*}{m_{2p}^*} = 3,1, \quad m_{1p}^* = 0,49m_0, \quad m_{2p}^* = 0,16m_0.$$

Germanium for from experience received prices is as follows:

$$m_{1p}^* = 0,34m_0, \quad m_{2p}^* = 0,04m_0, \quad \frac{m_{1p}^*}{m_{2p}^*} = \sim 8.$$

Valent zone the third branch for of energy k from _ addition is quadratic:

$$E_3(\vec{k}) = -E_{s_0} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_0} Ak^2, \quad (8)$$

here E_{s_0} - spin - orbital of fragmentation price and silicon _ 0.035 eV for germanium _ for and 0.28 eV. From (8). it seems that the third arm for effective

mass scalar quantity is: $m_{3p}^* = \frac{m_0}{A}$, silicon for

$m_{3p}^* = 0,24m_0$, germanium for $m_{3p}^* = 0,077m_0$. It is obvious that this _ branch for isoenergetic surfaces sphere is in the form of

b) Intermetallic combinations. III and V group of the elements from the combination generated ($A^{III}B^V$ type compounds (substances) (to them intermetallic combinations is called) semiconductor to the property they have This to class belongs to which is combinations they are: *GaAs*, *InSb*, *GaP*, *GaSb* and etc. _

Intermetallic of compounds zone structure theoretical calculation the fourth group of the elements zone structure with comparative in copy is being conducted. This with him is related that _ $A^{III}B^V$ type combinations zinc sulfide (*ZnS*) crystal structure on crystal-lizes . *ZnS* crystal structure to work Diamond from the structure only *A* and *B* type of atoms queue with

each other _ substitute to do with differs . Of this is the result that is intermetallic of compounds crystal cage periodic area inversion to the center owner not, that is $U(\vec{r}) \neq U(-\vec{r})$. of the case in the solution intermetallic of the merger crystal cage periodic potential compilation while doing zone structure known which is suitable IV group of the element from its potential use is $A^{III}B^V$ being combination of potential suitable IV group of the element potential with each which exciting antisymmetric of potential total whom is taken IV group of the element known structure this exciting the effect of the field (potential). under Yes whom to change visit certain is done. So, $A^{III}B^V$ type of the merger potential so becomes:

$$U^{III-V}(\vec{r}) = U_S^{IV-IV}(\vec{r}) + U_a^{IV-IV}(\vec{r}) + [\Delta U_S(\vec{r}) + \Delta U_a(\vec{r})],$$

here

$$U_S^{IV-IV}(\vec{r}) = U_S^{IV-IV}(-\vec{r}), \quad U_a^{IV-IV}(\vec{r}) = -U_a^{IV-IV}(-\vec{r})$$

, I mean U_S and $U_a - A^{IV}B^{IV}$ for " combination". of potential suitable as symmetrical and antisymmetric part of ΔU_S and ΔU_a to work of excitement symmetrical and antisymmetric is part of The issue in the solution

BN combination for don't buy zone structure (carbon " C " diamond modification), *GaAs* for *Ge*-flour , *AIP* for *Si*- flour , *InSb* for $\alpha - Sn$ - flour

structure main is taken $A^{III}B^V$ type of compounds one how many zone structure 4th on the picture is shown . Here conductivity zone structure qualitatively silicon and of germanium zone from the structure does not differ. Valent zone too three consists of a branch

(zone), itself too the third zone (V_3) spin orbital reciprocal influence as a result breaking apart the one two from the zone interspersed (down fell). Intermetallic of compounds valent zone different aspect from him consists of that is light and heavy to the holes suitable coming first two zone (V_1 and V_2) potential of the field

antisymmetric part with related as, Brillüen zone in the center ($\vec{k} = 0$) it breaks down. He is that is light and heavy of holes of energy maximum each other _ relatively it slides and Brilliant zone from the center one up to aside falls _ Himself too be can that every _ two maximum , or too From them one $\vec{k} = 0$ to the point out of consideration slipped let it be However one the rule

as sliding he up to small happens that _ $\vec{k} = 0$ at the point and maximum at the point of energy prices 1 eV apart from each other _ per cent one and either in a thousand one up to differs . Most little sliding *InSb* and *InAs*- too observation is being 4 *b* in the picture

InSb combination of valent zone structure one up to detail with given _ As seen as , valent zone maximum with conductor of the zone definitely minimum the same at the time Brilliant zone to the center ($k = 0$) falls.

Minimum near around energy $\vec{k}$ from _ parabolic on the picture depends, itself too of the zone at the bottom located of the electron effective mass many small

is ($m_n^* = 0,013 m_0$ cyclotron resonance from measurements received is the price).

Figure 4. Zone of $A^{III} B^V$ type compounds structure (a) and valence band structure (b)

For relatively large values of energy, the conduction zone is no longer parabolic and its curvature decreases. Therefore, the effective mass of the electron depends on the degree of filling of this zone. This, in turn, depends on the temperature and the concentration of additives.

$$\left(E - \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m_0} \right) \left(E - \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m_0} + \Delta E_g \right) \left(E - \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m_0} + \Delta E_g + E_{s_0} \right) - k^2 P^2 \left(E - \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m_0} + \Delta E_g + \frac{2}{3} E_{s_0} \right) = 0, \quad (9)$$

where E - the energy of the charge carrier, E_{s_0} - spin-orbital splitting, P - is a constant that takes into account the interaction of the conduction and valence band.

The limit can be ignored when the effective mass is very small. ($m_n^* \ll m_0$) $\frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m_0}$. Then from (9):

$$k^2 = \frac{E(E + \Delta E_g)(E + \Delta E_g + E_{s_0})}{P^2 \left(E + E_g + \frac{2}{3} E_{s_0} \right)} \quad (10)$$

This dependence is called an expression derived from the three-zone Kane model.

$InSb$ in the combination of E_{s_0} - is large, after making a series of simplifications, we can express the dependence of the energy on the wave vector for the conduction zone as follows:

$$E(\vec{k}) = \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m_n^*} (1 - \alpha k^2) \quad (11)$$

where $\alpha = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_n^* \Delta E_g}$ from the parabolicity of

the conduction zone is a parameter characterizing the deviation.

into account the interaction of the conduction and valence zones in the compound, Kane showed that the expression of the energy for different zones should $InSb$ be calculated from such a cubic equation:

Conclusion

The importance of semiconductors in the development of the national economy is great. Until 1948, very little was known about semiconductors. The ways of their use were discovered later. So, along with the progress of other fields of science, the science of semiconductors has developed and reached its current level. Previously, research was conducted on only one semiconductor crystal, but now the number of these crystals has increased significantly. Currently, with the help of these crystals, it is possible to convert heat and solar energy directly into electrical energy, as well as convert electrical energy into mechanical energy or vice versa without the use of machines, create coldness with electric current and achieve thermodynamic heating, store high-frequency electric and magnetic energies in reserve, etc. such fundamental issues are resolved. The following semiconductor elements are used to solve these problems. Silicon is the first widely used semiconductor material. Germanium is also a typical representative of the group of semiconducting elements. Germanium is superior to silicon in certain properties as a semiconductor material. Using it, diodes and triodes used in radio engineering are produced.

The silicon element is also widely used as a semiconductor. Photocells made on its basis have a high efficiency compared to other types of photocells.

Devices made of semiconductor elements are used in many areas of the national economy. One of these

fields is radio engineering. The reason for the use of semiconductors in radio engineering is their valuable properties known to us. The most important of these features are small size, high mechanical strength of semiconductor devices, low power requirement for operation. Diodes are one of the semiconductor devices used in radio engineering. These are p-n junction semiconductors. With the help of this semiconductor, alternating current can be converted into direct current. "Tunnel" diodes are also widely used in radio engineering.

References

1. V. Hajiyeva. Electron theory of semiconductors, Baku, 2022.
2. MZ Arbelyev. Physics of semiconductors, Baku, 2008.
3. A. Abdinov, I. Hasanov, T.X., Huseynov "Electronic devices and fundamentals of emission electronics". Baku, 2011.